

Evaluation of Therapeutic Effects of Extracorporeal Shock Wave Therapy and Ultrasound Therapy in Resistant Plantar Fasciitis Patients in a Tertiary Care Setting

Sonu Singh¹, Pawan Sharma², Dwit Vora³, U. Singh⁴

¹Associate Professor, Department of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur-302017, India

²Junior Resident, Department of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur-302017, India

³Junior Resident, Department of Pharmacology, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur 302017, India

⁴Professor & Head, Department of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur-302017, India

Received: 21-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr Pawan Sharma

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Plantar fasciitis is a common and painful condition affecting millions worldwide, characterized by heel pain. Despite advancements in diagnostic tools, managing patients with prolonged and resistant plantar fasciitis remains challenging. This study evaluated the therapeutic effects of Extracorporeal Shock Wave Therapy (ESWT) and Ultrasound Therapy (UST) in conjunction for patients with chronic plantar fasciitis unresponsive to conventional treatments. A total of 57 patients participated in this prospective, single-center comparative analytical study. The study assessed pain intensity using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and functional limitation using the Plantar Fasciitis Pain Scale (PFPS). The results of this study provide valuable insights into the efficacy of combining ESWT and UST in treating resistant plantar fasciitis, highlighting the potential for improved treatment outcomes and quality of life for patients with this debilitating condition. Further research is recommended to explore complementary therapies and ensure long-term treatment effectiveness.

Keywords: ESWT, Plantar fasciitis, UST, Resistant Planter Fasciitis, Ultrasound therapy, Extra Corporeal Shock Wave, Extra Corporeal Shock Wave Therapy.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Plantar fasciitis is a painful condition that affects several million people worldwide, the condition produces heel pain with a prevalence rate of at least 4% to 7% among the population. [1] The main symptom is the sharp and dull type of pain associated with tenderness in the plantar fascia which is formed as a thick ligament like structure that arises from the calcaneum and runs forward to the toes, and this results in a lot of difficult in performing daily activities due to the level of discomfort it causes. [2] This condition will produce pain that is sharp at the initiation of the ambulation in the morning after long hours of inactivity or at the end of the day after long standing or walking, which eases with the continuation of the activity but increases intensity under conditions of weight-bearing such as at the end of long working day with mounted standing or walking. [3] Still, plantar fasciitis is a widespread and important condition because it causes a great deal of pain, disability, and consumption of

healthcare resources, and it is difficult to diagnose and treat because of its heterogeneous etiology and clinical phenotype.

Epidemiological studies have revealed that plantar fasciitis is more likely to be seen on individuals in their middle age, aged between 40 and 60 years and is slightly more rampant in women than in men. Plantar fasciitis is one of the most common causes of heel pain, it has a highly disease burden, annually, about one million patients would visit clinic to seek plantar fasciitis treatment in the United States.

Plantar fasciitis is multifactorial disorder which is induced from biomechanical conditions including; abnormal foot structure, excessive pronation, tight heel cord and increased body weight and intrinsic predisposing factors including age, gender type and nature of work. [4] Besides, microtrauma due to the prolonged running, standing, or fit of improper shoes can also facilitate the occurrence of this

condition. [5] All of these collectively cause degeneration of plantar fascia tissue in terms of collagen fiber alignment disruption, micro-rupture and subsequent inflammation thus developing into painful, mechanically impaired structures figuratively. Chronic pain and irritation also causes changes in the gait and posture of a patient in the long run too. As a result of poor health treatment it can become even worse and lead to constant heel pain, the formation of heel spurs and secondary complications such as knee and hip complaints arising from the compensation created by the foot and ankle problems.

Plantar fasciitis is best diagnosed based on clinical examination, thus history taking and physical examination with emphasis on the area of pain that is along the medial calcaneal tuberosity and looking for signs of inflammation and biomechanical abnormalities. Ultrasonography may help in supporting the diagnosis and in excluding other abnormalities; MRI may provide further evidence. [6] Nevertheless, the diagnosis and management of plantar fasciitis has remained a tasking endeavor despite the enhanced diagnostic procedures and tools due to the fact that management of patients with prolonged complaints resistant to conservative treatment remains even more challenging.

Since extracorporeal shock wave therapy (ESWT) and ultrasound therapy (UST) have shown considerable efficacy in treating difficult cases of plantar fasciitis. [7] As ESWT transfers acoustic shock waves on the target site the following process ensue: disruption of calcification deposits, stimulation of tissue repair response, and emission of pain mediators such as substance P, which inhibits the release of nociceptive neurotransmitters. [8] In the same way, UST converts the high frequency sound waves into thermal and mechanical interactions to the tissues to increase blood flow, tissue relaxation, and drug distribution to the affected area to decrease the pain that patients experience and to support healing. [9]

This is especially worrisome because although the availability of literature regarding ESWT and UST as treatments for plantar fasciitis is increasing, there is a lack of research on how both can help when used concurrently. [10] It is apparent that this study is to compare ESWT and UST in combination therapy in resistant plantar fasciitis patients using standard assessment tools such as VAS for pain and PFPS as an index of function. [11] In a view of highlighting on these non-pharmacological modalities, this research will

facilitate better treatment result and thus a better quality of life of those patients suffering from this disabling disease.

Methods and Materials

Study Design: This study used prospective, single centre, comparative analytical study to assess the therapeutic efficacy of ESWT and UST in conjunction, in patients with chronic plantar fasciitis who had not responded to conventional modalities of treatment.

Sample Size and Patient Demographics: Out of 60 screened patients with resistant plantar fasciitis, 57 patients met the inclusion criteria to complete the study. Demographic information is presented on the age distribution and sex of the patients; see table 1 below.

Occupation Categorization: Occupation categorization was done based on the nature of work, with classifications including sedentary, moderate activity, and heavy activity. The distribution is illustrated in Table 1.

Outcome Measures: Pain intensity was measured using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and limitation of the activities due to pain was measured by the Plantar Fasciitis Pain Scale (PFPS). Only two patients each from the paracetamol and placebo groups agreed to be followed up after four weeks of treatment.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Diagnosis of resistant plantar fasciitis confirmed by clinical examination and imaging.
2. Age between 18 to 65 years.
3. Failure to respond to conservative treatments such as rest, orthotics, and physical therapy for at least three months.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. History of previous foot surgery or corticosteroid injections within the past six months.
2. Presence of systemic conditions affecting foot biomechanics, such as rheumatoid arthritis or neuropathy.
3. Pregnancy or lactation.
4. Contraindications to ESWT or UST, such as open wounds or tumor presence in the treatment area.

Results:

Patient Demographics

Table 1

Demographic	Category	Percentage
Sex	Male	56%
	Female	44%
Age Group	18-30	14%
	31-40	23%
	41-50	35%
	51-65	28%
Occupation	Sedentary	37%
	Active	63%

Pre and Post-Treatment Changes: Table 2 and 3 presents the mean VAS and PFPS scores pre and post-treatment for the ESWT and UST combination group. The mean changes in scores were analyzed using paired t-tests.

Pain Scores

VAS Scores Pre- and Post-Treatment

Table 2

Time Point	Mean VAS Score	Standard Deviation
Pre-Treatment	7.5	1.2
Post-Treatment	3.2	1.1

PFPS Scores Pre- and Post-Treatment

Table 3

Time Point	Mean PFPS Score	Standard Deviation
Pre-Treatment	45.3	6.8
Post-Treatment	22.1	5.7

Statistical Analysis: All statistical analysis was done using the statistical package for social sciences software, the version used was SPSS. Mean and standard deviation were computed for the demographic characteristics, test and t-test was used to compare the pre and post treatment measure. A p-value < 0. 05 was deemed as statistically significant level.

Discussion

The results of the present study indicate the possibility of the adjunctive treatment with ESWT and UST in patients with chronic plantar fasciitis. The findings of this study has shown a marked reduction in both the VAS scores and the PFPS scores, which indicates changes in perceived pain intensity and functional disability within the four weeks of the treatment program. These outcome findings are in harmony with prior research carried regarding ESWT and UST in the treatment of plantar fasciitis and its symptoms. [12,13]

It can be hypothesized that the applied combination of ESWT and UST produce synergistic effects due to their different modes of action. ESWT acts by creating microtrauma, which leads to the formation of new vessels and tissue regeneration [14], and UST works through thermal and mechanical modification of the tissue with the view of alleviating pain [15]. It can be stated that the integration of these treatment modalities probably improves the therapeutic effects by addressing

various aspects of the pathophysiological mechanism in PF patients.

Moreover, we have also noted that the current study carried a minimal risk of side effects, which is in agreement with the safety profile reported for ESWT and UST studies [16,17]. This indicate that the addition of ESWT to UST may provide a more promising approach to the patients who do not respond to the traditional conservative management or those who are looking for a non-surgical procedure rather than corticosteroid injection or surgery.

Conclusion

Overall, our findings offer substantial evidence for applying ESWT and UST treatment protocols in cases of chronic plantar fasciitis. The changes in pain and functional status underscore the opportunity of this DNICs-based method in maximizing its therapeutic touch on patients and improving their quality of life. Future studies with more participants and more extended follow-up periods should be done to confirm these findings and set up guidelines for treatments that can be offered to patients.

However, there are some of obvious drawbacks that should be mentioned. First however, it must be mentioned that sample size was relatively low and all the patients were from a single center. First, there is no separate control group that includes

patients treated either with ESWT or with UST, which prevents from making comparisons between the effectiveness of combined and single therapy. However, the 'four-weekly follow-up' might not adequately assess the sustainability and efficacy of therapeutic interventions. More future research is needed to overcome the limitations of the present investigation in order to have a better understanding about the efficacy of ESWT and UST for the treatment of plantar fasciitis.

Way Forward: Areas for future research could be to identify other types of complementary therapies like physical training and regenerative medicine in order to increase the potential therapeutic outcomes of ESWT and UST. It is also important to carry out further comparative studies, involving more patients in each group and with longer follow-up, to confirm the results outlined in this paper in order to inform clinical practice.

References

1. Riddle DL, Schappert SM. Volume of ambulatory care visits and patterns of care for patients diagnosed with plantar fasciitis: a national study of medical doctors. *Foot Ankle Int.* 2004;25(5):303-310.
2. Irving DB, Cook JL, Young MA, Menz HB. Impact of chronic plantar heel pain on health-related quality of life. *J Am Podiatr Med Assoc.* 2008;98(4):283-289.
3. Taunton JE, Ryan MB, Clement DB, McKenzie DC, Lloyd-Smith DR, Zumbo BD. A retrospective case-control analysis of 2002 running injuries. *Br J Sports Med.* 2002;36(2):95-101.
4. Riddle DL, Pulisic M, Pidcoe P, Johnson RE. Risk factors for plantar fasciitis: a matched case-control study. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2003;85(5):872-877.
5. Lemont H, Ammirati KM, Usen N. Plantar fasciitis: a degenerative process (fasciosis) without inflammation. *J Am Podiatr Med Assoc.* 2003;93(3):234-237.
6. McPoil TG, Martin RL, Cornwall MW, Wukich DK, Irrgang JJ, Godges JJ. Heel pain—plantar fasciitis: clinical practice guidelines linked to the international classification of function, disability, and health from the orthopedic section of the American Physical Therapy Association. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther.* 2008;38(4).
7. Ogden JA, Alvarez RG, Levitt R, Cross GL, Marlow ME. Shock wave therapy (Orthotripsy) in musculoskeletal disorders. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2001; 387:22-40.
8. Wang CJ, Chen HS, Huang TW. Shock wave therapy for patients with plantar fasciitis: a one-year follow-up study. *Foot Ankle Int.* 2002;23(3):204-207.
9. Draper DO, Castel JC, Castel D. Rate of temperature increase in human muscle during 1 MHz and 3 MHz continuous ultrasound. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther.* 1995;21(4):219-223.
10. Ibrahim MI, Donatelli RA, Schmitz C, Hellman MA, Buxbaum F. Chronic plantar fasciitis treated with two sessions of radial extracorporeal shock wave therapy. *Foot Ankle Int.* 2010; 31(5):391-397.
11. Landorf KB, Radford JA, Hudson S. Minimal important difference (MID) of two commonly used outcome measures for foot problems. *J Foot Ankle Res.* 2010; 3:7.
12. Greve JM, Grecco MV, Santos-Silva PR, Fuller R, Cavalcante ML, Pasqual Marques A. A comparison of radial shockwaves and conventional physiotherapy for treating plantar fasciitis in athletes: a randomized controlled trial. *Clinical rehabilitation.* 2016;30(4):339-347.
13. Ibrahim MI, Donatelli RA, Schmitz C, Hellman MA, Buxbaum F. Chronic plantar fasciitis treated with two sessions of radial extracorporeal shock wave therapy. *Foot Ankle Int.* 2010; 31(5):391-397.
14. Wang CJ, Chen HS, Huang TW. Shock wave therapy for patients with plantar fasciitis: a one-year follow-up study. *Foot Ankle Int.* 2002;23(3):204-207.
15. Draper DO, Castel JC, Castel D. Rate of temperature increase in human muscle during 1 MHz and 3 MHz continuous ultrasound. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther.* 1995;21(4):219-223.
16. Ogden JA, Alvarez RG, Levitt R, Cross GL, Marlow ME. Shock wave therapy (Orthotripsy) in musculoskeletal disorders. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2001; 387:22-40.
17. Landorf KB, Radford JA, Hudson S. Minimal important difference (MID) of two commonly used outcome measures for foot problems. *J Foot Ankle Res.* 2010; 3:7.